

Research Paper

Dutch farmers' views on public and private incentives for soil health improvements

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Dutch farmers evaluated incentives to improve soil health.
- Most farmers prefer private contracts for soil improvements
- Carbon farming contracts appeal to a smaller farmer segment
- CAP payments are evaluated as unattractive
- Traditional farmers remain hard to motivate despite incentives

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

CONTEXT: Attention to soil health has increased in recent years. Healthier soils can result from extensifying farming practices which increase soil organic matter, and research shows that farmers often need to be financially incentivized to implement such practices. Financial incentives can be provided through agri-environmental contracts between farmers and public entities, through payments from food value chain actors for more sustainable production, or more recently, also through payments from carbon credit markets.

OBJECTIVE: This article aims to provide insights into how farmers perceive various financial incentives, including public payments, payments along the food value chain, and payments through carbon credit markets, as well as non-financial incentives (e.g., improved training opportunities).

METHOD: The article is based on the results of a Q Methodology experiment with 22 Dutch farmers.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS: The analysis identifies three different perspectives. The article discusses the primary characteristics of farmers who share a common perspective and comments on the results within the context of Dutch agriculture. The results suggest that farmers within the sample display a greater interest in private contracts with value chain payments (*pro-environmental entrepreneurs*), that some farmers are interested in the opportunity to sell carbon credits (*carbon farming pragmatics*), and that others (*traditional food providers*) are not easily to motivate by any of the incentives.

SIGNIFICANCE: Overall, a diverse set of incentives will be necessary to encourage farmers to improve soil health and carbon sequestration in soils.

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1. Introduction

Soils are the foundation of our food system. They provide essential ecosystem services such as food, feed, fibre, water regulation, and nutrients for plants. In addition, healthy soils store carbon and help mitigate the effects of global warming. However, the quality of soils in the EU, as indicated by the soil organic matter content or soil biodiversity, is declining; roughly 60 % of EU soils are in poor condition (European Commission, 2023b). The decline in soil health is primarily due to human activities that lead to over-fertilisation, compaction, or contamination (European Commission, 2023b). In the Netherlands, intensive agriculture, characterized by monocultures for feed production (e.g., maize), the overuse of pig manure, and heavy machinery are important causes of soil degradation (Kik et al., 2024; Recare-Hub, 2018).

Specific measures on arable land, such as reduced tillage, cover crops, improved fertiliser planning, crop rotations, and arable land conversion to grassland, help to improve soil quality (Braitto et al., 2020; Kik et al., 2024), and are among the measures identified as the most promising to improve soil health on typical Dutch arable farms (Kik et al., 2024). These measures classify more extensification of agricultural systems, and often farmers need to be financially incentivized to implement them (e.g., Mamine et al., 2020; Schaub et al., 2023; Schulze et al., 2023; Weituschat et al., 2023). Financial incentives can come from public sources; for instance, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) requires the fulfilment of enhanced conditionality requirements to access direct payments, and financial support for targeted, more ambitious nature protection activities is provided via agri-environmental schemes (AES) (European Commission, 2023a). Another option to provide financial incentives are private contracts with actors within the food value chain. An example of this is the Barilla sustainable farming project, which is focused on soil health and offers higher prices to farmers producing under the company's sustainable farming scheme (Barilla, 2022; Global Compact, 2015). A relatively new financial incentive comes from carbon credit trading. The EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Regulation (EU/2024/3012) determines the requirements for EU carbon credit certification and trade (European Commission, 2024). Carbon credits are certified *carbon removal units*, where one unit represents one tonne of certified net carbon removal (McDonald et al., 2021).

This article aims to investigate how farmers perceive various incentives that reward improvements in soil health and carbon sequestration on farmland, as well as the underlying beliefs that shape their perceptions. It presents the results of a Q Methodology experiment with 22 Dutch farmers. Q Methodology was developed by Stephenson (1953) and enables the analysis of subjectivity. Q Methodology experiments are well-suited for studying social phenomena that can lead to conflict, such as environmental issues (Barry and Proops, 1999). From a theoretical perspective, discourse theory provides the foundation for the assumptions underlying the experiment. Discourse theory examines how a discourse is constructed and how it influences society (McCaug et al., 2023).

Barry and Proops (1999) discuss how research is effective in identifying problems (e.g., declining soil health) and potential responses (e.g., improvements in soil health through less intensive management), but often fails to implement these changes effectively. They highlight that Q Methodology enables the assessment of a discourse on a topic and allows for identifying promising incentives that should be further assessed or implemented. Q Methodology experiments have already been applied to similar contexts, for example, by Davies and Hodge (2007) and Braitto et al. (2020). Davies and Hodge (2007) analyse how farmers perceive their roles in environmental management, for instance, whether they feel responsible for providing public goods. Braitto et al. (2020) determine farmers' views on soil management and the influential factors that affect their soil-management decisions. Both confirm that farmers respond differently to various (financial) incentives and that some

farmers perceive it as their responsibility to provide public goods.

A growing body of research has applied Q Methodology to investigate farmers' views on soil health-friendly practices (Braitto et al., 2020) and broader sustainable farm management approaches (Iofrida et al., 2018). Some of these studies also explore incentive types that aim to reward such improvements, including payments through the CAP (e.g., Braitto et al., 2020; Iofrida et al., 2018) and carbon credit trading schemes (Opdenbosch et al., 2025). In addition, various studies have employed other preference elicitation methods, such as Discrete Choice Experiments, to examine farmers' preferences for CAP payments (e.g., Lapierre et al., 2023; Villanueva et al., 2017), carbon credit trading (e.g., Aslam et al., 2017; Block et al., 2024), and value chain contracts (e.g., Weituschat et al., 2023) as mechanisms to incentivise soil health improvements.

Although review articles summarising farmers' perceptions of different incentive types (or contract solutions) exist (Bredemeier et al., 2022), it remains uncommon for studies to ask farmers to compare multiple incentive types within a single experiment (Bradfield et al., 2023). Understanding these preferences is essential, particularly given that dominant CAP payment schemes have shown limited effectiveness in driving behavioural change and delivering environmental benefits (Bredemeier et al., 2022). The experiment underlying this article first informed farmers about soil health practices that can lead to carbon sequestration, the standards required for EU-certified carbon credits, and the underlying requirements for CAP payments and for private contracts with actors in the food value chain. Next, the participants were asked to order 36 statements in a Q sorting grid, their sorting indicated the extent to which they agreed or disagreed with each individual statement. The statements referred to farmers' management decisions, their attitudes towards environmental protection, and the three analysed incentive mechanisms. The results are expected to be of interest to policymakers, as they demonstrate that different incentives and their combinations are necessary to motivate farmers to improve soil health and carbon sequestration on farmland. Furthermore, the study suggests that it will be challenging to motivate farmers with traditional viewpoints.

The article is structured as follows. First, the Q Methodology and the setup of the experiment are described (Section 2). Next, the results are presented in Section 3, followed by a critical discussion in Section 4.

2. The Q methodology experiment

Q Methodology typically involves six steps: (i) identification of the area of the 'discourse', (ii) identification of the discourse, (iii) statement selection, (iv) conducting the experiment, (v) experiment analysis, and (vi) interpretation. Steps i.-v. are outlined in the next section. The last step is reported in the results and discussion sections.

2.1. Area of the discourse – soil health, carbon farming, and financial incentives

According to Laishram et al. (2012), healthy soils function as a vital living system within their ecosystem and land-use boundaries. The current soil health status determines the soil's ability to fulfil important functions, and is closely linked to the soil organic carbon content. Hence, soil organic carbon can be an indicator of soil health. Soil organic carbon content determines soil structure and the availability of water and nutrients (Lal, 2016). Carbon content and therefore soil health on farmland can be increased by applying more extensive farming practices, for instance, by reducing tillage, using cover and catch crops, or converting arable land to grassland (COWI et al., 2021; McDonald et al., 2021). These practices contribute to the accumulation of organic matter, which is essential for generating certified carbon credits under the EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Regulation. Thus, improving soil health through extensive management practices is not only beneficial for soil functioning but also a prerequisite for

participating in carbon credit markets, making the two concepts interconnected.

Carbon farming refers to all activities where farmers and land users achieve the following outcomes: carbon removal and storage in biomass or soils, the avoidance of future CO₂ and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, or the reduction of existing CO₂ and GHG emissions. Examples of carbon farming practices include (i) afforestation and reforestation, (ii) agroforestry and other forms of mixed farming (e.g., silvopasture), (iii) soil health measures on arable land (for instance, reduced tillage, cover crops, improved fertiliser planning, arable land conversion to grassland), and (iv) the rewetting and restoration of peatlands (McDonald et al., 2021). The implementation of carbon farming measures leads to improvements in soil health. However, not all measures relevant to soil health, such as machines that reduce soil compaction, result in carbon removals. Various monetary incentives can support carbon farming activities and soil health-friendly farming.

Public funding for environmentally friendly farm management is, for instance, granted through the CAP. Payments for ecosystem services can be financed through either Pillar I, the European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF) or Pillar II, the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD). These two funding pillars result in payment schemes with distinct characteristics. Payments granted under the first pillar are, for example, annual, while payments granted under the second pillar are multi-annual (European Commission, 2023a).

Farmers must comply with specific conditions to receive CAP payments. The ‘enhanced conditionality’ consists of statutory management requirements that aim at sustainable farming. The measures of the enhanced conditionality aim at good agricultural and environmental conditions (GAEC) (European Commission, 2023a). Some of the requirements (e.g., cover crops, wider crop rotations, restrictions on tillage) may provide benefits for soils and lead to carbon sequestration.

Schemes for the climate, the environment, and animal welfare (eco-schemes) are new tools to deliver the goals set by the European Commission. Practices can only qualify to become eco-schemes when they require management adjustments that go beyond the legislative requirements and the enhanced conditionality (European Commission, 2023a). In the Netherlands, eco-schemes are implemented using a result-based point system, where each activity converts into eco-points. The eco-points translate into per-hectare payments if they exceed a certain threshold value (Jongeneel and Gonzalez-Martinez, 2023).

More stringent management restrictions are supported by the second pillar of the CAP. These measures are commonly referred to as agri-environmental schemes (AES) and include, for instance, payments for peatland rewetting, agroforestry, or the conversion to organic farming (European Commission, 2023a). Measures financed through the second pillar are multi-annual, lasting five years because the environmental goals require longer and more complex engagement (Guyomard et al., 2023). Since 2016, Dutch farmer collectives have been responsible for implementing AES. The approach is believed to motivate farmers to enhance the spatial coordination of measures (Barghusen et al., 2021).

Carbon markets for certified carbon credits might provide new funding opportunities for soil health-friendly management. Carbon credits are certified ‘carbon removal units’, where one unit represents one tonne of certified net carbon removals (McDonald et al., 2021). The EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Regulation (EU/2024/3012) determines the requirements for EU carbon credit certification and trade (European Commission, 2024). The regulation stipulates that certified carbon credits must meet the so-called Q.U.A.L.I.T.Y criteria. In brief, the removals need to be **quantified** in an accurate and robust manner, generating a net carbon removal benefit that is **additional** (at least above the existing legal requirements). They should ensure the **long-term storage** of carbon and have a neutral impact, or even a co-benefit, for other **sustainability** objectives.

More specifically, **quantification** entails that carbon removals must be quantified in a manner that is relevant, accurate, complete, consistent, and comparable. Third-party auditing plays a crucial role in

ensuring the credibility and reliability of carbon removals. To quantify the net carbon removal benefit, a two-step process is employed. First, the gross amount of additional carbon removals generated by a carbon removal activity compared to a baseline is calculated, using standardised baselines. These baselines reflect the typical performance of similar activities in comparable social, economic, environmental, technological, and geographical contexts, aiming for objectivity, minimal compliance costs, and recognition of early movers. Second, any increase in greenhouse gas emissions associated with the implementation of the carbon removal activity is deducted. These emissions may arise from increased use of fertilisers, chemicals, fuel, energy, or changes in practices. The second criterion, **additionality**, ensures that activities exceed statutory requirements. Therefore, the standardised baseline for farmers should reflect the carbon emissions of farms complying with existing legislative frameworks. Given that almost all farmers receive CAP payments, the enhanced conditionality requirements of the CAP also need to be exceeded. **Long-term storage** means that carbon storage should be permanent. This is defined as a centuries-long process and may be achieved through methods such as geological storage or carbon mineralisation. However, different carbon removal activities vary in processes, storage mediums, and timescales. Carbon farming on arable land, peatland rewetting, or afforestation is considered to lead to carbon removals that span decades. The last criterion, **sustainability**, requires that carbon farming should not only mitigate climate change but ideally offer co-benefits for sustainability. This requirement ensures that carbon removal activities have a neutral or positive impact on other sustainability objectives such as biodiversity, water, and marine resource protection. More specifically, the sustainability criterion disqualifies practices such as afforestation with monocultures that harm biodiversity (European Commission, 2024).¹

The key carbon farming methods include afforestation, agroforestry, peatland rewetting and soil health measures, such as reduced tillage (McDonald et al., 2021). Peatlands comprise 34 % of agricultural emissions in the Netherlands (Norris et al., 2021). However, rewetting can render them unsuitable for farming (Wetlands International, 2023). Soil health measures that allow continued agricultural production may be favoured by farmers but can face challenges such as reversibility. Therefore, peatland rewetting, afforestation, and agroforestry are seen as the most promising carbon farming options (COWI et al., 2021; McDonald et al., 2021), while soil health measures received a more critical evaluation (Buck and Palumbo-Compton, 2022; Paul et al., 2023).

Contacts aiming at soil health improvements can also exist between stakeholders within the **food value chain** (e.g., supermarkets or processors) and farmers. Harmanny and Schulp (2023) conducted a literature review and an online search to identify existing public and private funding schemes that promote environmental outcomes in the Netherlands. The study shows that more than 50 % of the contracts are either entirely private or funded by a combination of private and public sources. In general, contracts present binding agreements between two parties, which can be natural or legal entities (such as companies). They are typically based on country-specific frameworks and encompass multiple areas of law, providing the parties with a certain degree of legal certainty (Runge et al., 2022).

Value chain contracts for the provision of ecosystem services are often production contracts where farmers agree to deliver a product produced under specific standards. Payments for ecological aspects are typically not granted separately but are incorporated into a higher

¹ It should be noted that current private initiatives offering carbon credit certification often do not meet the Q.U.A.L.I.T.Y criteria. In the Netherlands, multiple private initiatives exist, one is by the farmers’ organisation ZLTO (ZLTO, 2024), another one is by Rabobank (Rabobank, 2022). ZLTO, for instance, offered contracts of five years only. Furthermore, farmers did not need to meet the additionality criterion.

Table 1
Statements and statement labels (source: own representation).

Nr.	Translated Statements	Labels
1	Soil health practices lead to reliable, long-term increases in soil organic carbon (Paul et al., 2023).	long-term increase
2	Soil health practices are part of good farm management (Buck and Palumbo-Compton, 2022).	good farm management
3	The public should remunerate investments in soil health as they lead to public goods (e.g., improvements in water quality, and biodiversity) (Bartkowski et al., 2022)	multiple public goods
4	Soil health measures make my farm more resilient against climate change (Barbato and Strong, 2023).	resilience climate change
5	Soil carbon content is of lower interest to me than soil structure, soil water holding capacity and lower soil erosion (Dumbrell et al., 2016).	soil structure
6	I would be open to planting trees and rewetting of my peatlands to sequester carbon (Dumbrell et al., 2016; European Commission, 2024).	hard measures
7	Additional training and education are good enough to motivate me to implement more soil health friendly practices (Braitto et al., 2020; Buck and Palumbo-Compton, 2022).	training & education
8	The whole food supply chain (farmers, producers, and consumers) needs to find solutions to finance additional soil health measures.	solutions food supply chain
9	I would find carbon farming contracts more attractive if my successors would be able to leave the contract (Rochecouste et al., 2017).	termination option
10	Long-term contracts would become more attractive if the payments were adjusted to inflation (Buck and Palumbo-Compton, 2022).	inflation
11	Contracts are more attractive if I can choose the measures I would like to implement (Herzon et al., 2018)	choose measures
12	Short-term land tenure contracts make it difficult for me to invest in soil health.	short tenure
13	I can commit to a contract with a longer runtime than 10 years (Harmanny and Schulp, 2023; Rochecouste et al., 2017).	long-term contracts
14	I would rather participate in carbon farming if the activities were organised by farmers' groups (e.g., an agricultural collective) (Terwan, 2016; Tiusanen et al., 2022)	farmers' groups
15	Farmers should cover the costs of soil sampling (Loomis and Gascoigne, 2018).	soil sampling costs
16	Result-based payments should exclude farmers with high carbon content in soils to promote additional action against climate change (Bartkowski et al., 2022; European Commission, 2024).	result-based
17	The costs of adjusting farm management need to be compensated through payments for the measures (Canales et al., 2024; Gramig and Widmar, 2018).	action-based payments
18	The payments offered over the CAP (AES and eco-schemes) are high enough to set good financial incentives (Braitto et al., 2020; Zimmermann and Britz, 2016).	CAP good incentives
19	AES and eco-schemes are for hobby farmers and those on poor-quality soils (Davies and Hodge, 2007).	hobby farmers
20	I believe there will be a viable carbon market in the future (Bougherara et al., 2023).	CM attractive
21	It would be a good incentive if combinations of payments from the CAP (AES and eco-schemes) and private payments (from the value chain or over carbon markets) would be allowed (Herzon et al., 2018).	payment combination
22	Existing initiatives for carbon farming (for example by Rabobank and ZLTO) will lose their participants if they tighten their requirements to fulfil the EU certification guidelines.	existing initiatives
23	Carbon markets for EU certified carbon credit are too risky (Canales et al., 2024; Barbato and Strong, 2023).	CM risky
24	Hybrid payments – that partly cover the costs of the measures and are partly based on outcomes (sequestered amounts) - are fair (Herzon et al., 2018).	hybrid payments
25	Next to voluntary initiatives (Eco-schemes, AES, value chain or carbon credit trade) the legislative framework needs to be tightened (Davies and Hodge, 2007).	legislation
26	High competition does not allow me to implement additional soil health practices (Schaub et al., 2023).	high competition
27	When I compare myself to nearby farmers – I am always open for new business models (Dessart et al., 2019).	entrepreneurial
28	To state that CO ₂ emissions are lowered by soil health practices is greenwashing (Paul et al., 2023).	greenwashing
29	Productivity is not my main priority, when deciding on farm management practices (Braitto et al., 2020).	productivity
30	Farmers need to protect water and soils for future generations (Braitto et al., 2020; Davies and Hodge, 2007)s.	future generations
31	'Carbon farming' limits my freedom to run my farm as I wish (Davies and Hodge, 2007).	freedom to farm
32	I would accept that soil health practices may have a negative impact on my income in the short run (Kik et al., 2024).	short-term income
33	Farmers are both, producers of agricultural products and nature protectionists (Braitto et al., 2020).	nature protectionists
34	Dutch soils are in good conditions (additional soil health measures are not necessary) (Davies and Hodge, 2007)	soil conditions are good
35	Good agricultural practices mean finding a balance between nature protection and the production of agricultural goods (Braitto et al., 2020).	balance
36	I would like to focus more on agriculture and less on administrative aspects (e.g., contracts of any kind).	focus farming

product price. In addition to higher prices, farmers are often offered a purchase guarantee for specific volumes of their product. The downstream value chain actor (e.g., a supermarket) will usually cover the higher costs by selling the product at higher prices to consumers (Runge et al., 2022). To prevent consumers from being misled in their purchase decisions, the EU aims to ban greenwashing and unsupported claims. The use of claims such as 'eco-friendly', 'climate-neutral' or 'climate-friendly' will be forbidden from 2026 onwards when companies cannot prove via approved certification schemes that their offsets and biodiversity contributions are valid (European Parliament, 2023).

The payment mechanisms that are used for different incentives may also influence farmers' decisions. AES and eco-schemes and private payments over the value chain can be action-based, result-based, or hybrid. In contrast, carbon credits sold via carbon credit markets will lead to result-based payments. Generally, a payment is considered action-based when it rewards the required measures (e.g., reducing tillage or applying organic fertilisers). The amount of payment is usually based on the average income forgone when implementing the practice (Runge et al., 2022). In contrast, a scheme is considered result-based

when the reward is based on achieving a desired output (e.g., the amount of carbon stored per hectare). Since result-based schemes do not remunerate specific practices, farmers can usually choose the measures that they apply freely. Action-based payments have the advantage of being easier to monitor compared to result-based schemes. Farmers may also prefer this approach because it ensures payment. Result-based schemes, on the other hand, are generally considered to be more effective. Hybrid schemes aim to mitigate the drawbacks of purely result-based and purely action-based schemes. In hybrid schemes, a portion of the payment is fixed and based on the measures implemented. Hybrid schemes could, for instance, grant bonus payments when specific results are reached (Herzon et al., 2018).

2.2. Identification of the discourse & statement selection

The Q-concourse is a compilation of various perspectives on the topic. The concourse underlying the experiment is ready-made, meaning it is mainly based on a previously conducted literature review (Sandling, 2024). In addition to this, information from the webpages of farmers'

collectives offering AES participation or early trials on carbon credit trade, were included. First, all potential statements related to soil health, carbon credit trade, and value chain payments were collected. Next, the statements that were used for the experiment were selected as a subset of the Q-concourse. The included statements are commonly referred to as the Q-set (Akhtar-Danesh, 2018; Webler et al., 2009).

Webler et al. (2009) and Sandling (2024) emphasise that good Q Methodology statements should be relevant, meaningful, understandable, and significant to participants. The participants were informed that they should order the statements to provide information on their opinion about: “What motivates Dutch farmers to invest in soil health?”. The statements addressed various aspects of soil health, incentives for promoting soil health-friendly management, contractual details, farmers’ attitudes, potential challenges, and social expectations. Out of the initial Q-concourse, 36 statements were included in the experiment. Recent Q Methodology experiments with farmers used a similar number of statements, Davies and Hodge (2007) included 33 statements; Braitto et al. (2020) included 34 statements. The statements included in the experiment are displayed in Table 1. For those resulting from the literature review, the source is indicated. Each of the statements was assigned a label that is meant to summarise the statement’s core idea.

2.3. Conducting the experiment

The online platform Q Method Software (2024) was used to conduct the experiment. The data were collected during the winter and early spring of 2024 and 2025, a period selected because farmers are generally less busy on their farms. A dual approach was used to gather responses. Part of the data were collected face-to-face from 10 farmers, who were asked to complete the online survey independently using the Q Method Software. After completing the survey, they were invited to provide feedback on both the survey itself and the incentive types presented. These farmers were recruited through farm fairs, visits to farms near the university, and contacts in the student assistant’s hometown. Twelve responses were collected from arable farmers via a market research company with a strong agricultural focus. This method allowed for targeted outreach to arable farmers, who completed the survey online and independently, without direct interaction with the research team. This dual approach was chosen following the recommendation of Sandling (2024), who highlights the importance of face-to-face engagement. This method not only facilitates richer qualitative insights, especially when participants are asked to reflect on the topic after completing the survey, but also helps researchers interpret unexpected or complex viewpoints more effectively. Additionally, collecting ten responses face-to-face helped to develop expectations regarding the number and nature of viewpoints likely to emerge.

The online survey was structured as follows: First, the participants received the same information on what soil health is, what carbon farming entails (and that carbon farming does not refer solely to carbon credit trade), the measures that can be applied, the requirements that apply, and the incentives that can be provided. In this step, they had the choice to either watch a seven-minute video on the topic or to read the information.² The information provided to the participants is in the appendix, as it may have influenced farmers’ choices.³ The participants

² The study was pretested, and two options were included because the pre-test showed that some farmers disliked watching a video and preferred written information. In addition, some questions about the farm and farmer characteristics were shortened following the pre-test results.

³ The information on carbon credit trade, for instance, referred to soil sampling on the farm to determine the amount of carbon stored, and not to a comparison with a standardised baseline. This is a deviation from the EU’s regulation in place and must be considered when interpreting the results. The information provided on the payments from value chain partners is based on the information provided on their webpages (e.g. ZLTO, 2024)

then received information about the experiment’s aim and how to conduct it. Afterwards, farmers could decide to pre-sort the statements (initial sort) before performing the actual sorting into the Q-sorting grid. When pre-sorting the statements, they could choose between three categories: disagreement, neutral, and agreement. Afterwards, the participants were asked to sort the 36 statements into the Q-sorting grid that is shown in Fig. 1. The Q sorting grid had a quasi-normal distribution. Farmers were asked to place the statements based on their level of agreement or disagreement (the scale ranged from –5 to 5, representing most and least agreement) with the respective statement.

The statements were randomly presented to the farmers in the (pre-) sorting exercise. After finishing the sorting exercise, farmers were asked to provide information on themselves and their farms. A direct question on how to best financially incentivise farmers was also included (via (i) public funding, (ii) markets for EU-certified carbon credits, (iii) private contracts with value chain partners).

The sample includes 22 farmers. Brown (2003) advised to include no more than 40 participants in the analysis, while Webler et al. (2009) propose a typical sample size of 12 to 36. The Q Methodology experiments by Davies and Hodge (2007) included 100 farmers, while Braitto et al. (2020) analysed the responses from 34 participants. In general, it is argued that the experiment’s results can be improved by focusing on a more diverse rather than a larger sample. In this study, the extracted viewpoints closely reflect the verbal feedback provided during face-to-face interviews, reinforcing confidence in the sufficient size of the sample. Moreover, the time commitment required (roughly 40 min) to complete the online survey posed challenges for recruitment. This is reflected in the low response rate of just 2.5 % among farmers contacted online, even after receiving two reminder messages. In contrast, when farmers were approached face-to-face, the response rate increased significantly to 25 %, highlighting the importance of personal engagement in encouraging participation.

2.4. Experiment analysis

The estimation in the Q Methodology is an alternative form of factor analysis. Akhtar-Danesh (2018) or Watts and Stenner (2005) describe the analysis as a one-person factor analysis that focuses on identifying correlations among participants, and not among variables. Multiple software packages, such as *qfactor* for Stata or R, and the online tool Ken-Q-Analysis enable the analysis of data from Q Methodology experiments. This article uses the results from Ken-Q-Analysis.

In the analysis, similar, finalised sorting exercises (the Q-sorts) are clustered together. The first step of the analysis involves calculating a correlation matrix for the Q-sorts. The matrix shows the similarity among all finalised Q-sorts using a scale from –1 to 1. Next, different factor extraction methods, for instance, centroid factor analysis or principal component analysis, are applied to identify factors (Akhtar-Danesh, 2018; Sandling, 2024). Sandling (2024) recommends extracting seven factors as a starting point. The eigenvalues of each factor can be used to decide how many factors to analyse. One approach is to plot these eigenvalues and detect an ‘elbow’, where the function levels off. This elbow in the plot shows the optimal number of factors, as additional factors beyond the elbow provide limited additional explanation. Another approach is using the Kaiser-Guttman criterion, which postulates that factors with eigenvalues greater than 1 should be included in the final analysis. These add sufficiently to the explanatory power of the overall analysis (Barry and Proops, 1999; Sandling, 2024). Davies and Hodge (2007) included all factors in the final analysis when at least two Q-sorts loaded significantly on them. Braitto et al. (2020) combined the recommendations, their factors had an eigenvalue >1, at least two Q-sorts loading on them, and appeared to reflect the real world sufficiently well. This article applied the Kaiser-Guttman criterion; the resulting factors had at least two Q-sorts loading on them, and the factors seemed to display realistic, easily interpretable viewpoints.

Once the optimal number of factors is identified, factor loadings are

Fig. 1. Q-sorting grid used in the experiment (source: own representation).

estimated from the correlation matrix to determine the strength of association between each Q-sort and a factor (Sandling, 2024). A participant is considered to load on a factor if their factor loading is significant.⁴ The factor loading represents the correlation between the participant’s Q-sort and the factor (Akhtar-Danesh, 2018). To improve interpretation, factor rotation techniques (Varimax, Equamax, or Quartimax) are applied (Barry and Proops, 1999); they result, for instance, in different numbers of distinguishing statements per factor (Akhtar-Danesh, 2023), or allow to identify more useful factors overall as they affect which Q-sorts load on a factor (Davies and Hodge, 2007).

After determining the ideal number of factors, distinguishing statements are identified. A distinguishing statement is one whose z-factor score is significantly different from those of other factors; this is determined using *t*-tests. In contrast, consensus statements are not significantly different across factors, and neutral statements are neither distinguishing nor consensus and have unique sorting patterns (Akhtar-Danesh, 2018). The presented Q-sort values are weighted averages of statement rankings across all Q-sorts loading on the factor. When participants are strongly correlated with a factor, they receive a higher weight (Sandling, 2024). The distinguishing statements, and their Q-sort values are used to interpret the findings (Barry and Proops, 1999). The article presents the results from a principal component analysis followed by a Varimax rotation; the results from a centroid factor analysis only showed minor deviations.

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive statistics

Table 2 provides the descriptive statistics for the analysed sample. The participating farmers are, on average, 46 years old, and most of them are male (95 %). 73 % of farmers have a higher agricultural education (a university degree or HBO (Higher Professional Education)). Most of them operate their farms conventionally (82 %), and farm on 92 ha of land. Their most common soil type is clay (59 %). The estimated soil organic carbon content is estimated to be between 1 % and 3 % (41 %) or more than 3 % (45 %). Most of the farms had a secure succession

⁴ A participant is considered to significantly load on a factor when the correlation exceeds a threshold. This threshold is calculated as follows: $\sqrt{\frac{2.58}{\text{number of statements}}}$. Depending on the software, higher thresholds can be used to improve the interpretability of the analysis, as only Q-sorts strongly associated with a factor are considered to load, and fewer Q-sorts load on multiple factors (Akhtar-Danesh, 2018). The threshold applied in this study was 0.400. For the distinguishing statements, $p < 0.01$ was used to determine significance.

(68 %). When asked how they would classify their farms, 64 % chose arable farming, while fewer self-classified as dairy (23 %), mixed, or special crop farms (14 %). Examining their distribution across the 12 Dutch provinces, the sample is relatively well distributed. Five participants are from Friesland, four from Groningen, three from Noord-Brabant, three from Zeeland, two from Zuid-Holland, two from Gelderland, and two from Flevoland. Although the approach does not aim for representative samples, Table 2 also provides information on the averages found in the Dutch farming population for specific characteristics. This shows that more arable farms and farms on high-quality soils were included in the sample. In addition, the farms are relatively large.

Table 2

Summary of the descriptive statistics of the participants (source: own calculation).

Farm and farmer characteristics	Sample Mean	Dutch farming population	Source
Year of birth	1979		
Share of male participants	95 %		
Share of participants with university degrees	32 %		
Share of participants with HBO degrees (Higher professional education)	41 %		
Share of participants with MBO (Secondary vocational education), and other degrees	27 %		
Share of organic producers	18 %		
Hectares of the farm	92	42	van der Meulen (2024)
Share of arable farms	64 %	15 %	Voskuilen (2024)
Share of dairy farms	23 %	24 %	Voskuilen (2024)
Share of mixed farms, or special crops farms	14 %		
Soil organic carbon content <1.5 %	5 %		
Soil organic carbon content 1.5–3 %	41 %		
Soil organic carbon content >3 %	45 %		
Predominant soil type - sand	36 %	70 %	Silvius et al. (2016)
Predominant soil type – clay	59 %	17 %	Silvius et al. (2016)
Predominant soil type – loam / loess	5 %	13 %	Silvius et al. (2016)
Share of farms with secure succession	68 %		

Fig. 2. Plot of the eigenvalues of the extracted factors (source: own representation with Ken-Q Analysis).

3.2. Factor interpretation

During the analysis, different numbers of factors were extracted, and their explanatory power was assessed using eigenvalues. These eigenvalues are displayed in Fig. 2. The figure indicates that including more than three factors provides limited additional explanatory value, suggesting that a three-factor solution is optimal.

The three factors explain 54 % of the underlying variation in the responses. Out of the 22 responses, 18 of the 22 conducted Q-sorts load significantly on one factor, two Q-sorts do not meet the threshold, and two Q-sorts load significantly on two factors. Table 3 presents the factor loadings of the Q-sorts. Q-sorts that significantly load on a single factor are flagged, indicating that they help define that factor. In contrast, Q-sorts with significant loadings on multiple factors are not flagged, allowing for a clearer differentiation of distinct viewpoints (Zabala, 2014).

The names of the factors are based on the distinguishing statements of the identified factors and their factor values. Each factor reflects the views of like-minded participants. The first factor represents the *pro-environmental entrepreneurs*, with ten farmers loading on this factor. The second factor represents traditional food providers, with four farmers contributing to this factor. The third factor represents the *carbon farming pragmatics* (four farmers). Table 4 presents the average Q-sort values for the statements. A distinguishing statement has a score that is significantly different from the scores of at least one other factor. The higher the factor estimate (Q-sort value), the more strongly the statement is perceived (Akhtar-Danesh, 2018).

3.2.1. The pro-environmental entrepreneurs

There are 10 distinguishing statements for this factor; if we consider significance at the 0.05 level, this increases to 14.⁵ The *pro-environmental entrepreneurs* believe that soil health-friendly farming helps to make their enterprise more resilient against climate change (no. 4) and would even accept short-term income losses to improve their soil quality (no. 32). This may be connected to the perception that the quality of Dutch soils is relatively poor (no. 34), that soil health needs to be ensured for future generations (no. 30) or to their agreement that productivity is not

⁵ Ken-Q Analysis may label a statement as both distinguishing and consensus to reflect that, while it shows statistically significant differences between some factors, it is still interpreted as broadly consensual across the dataset.

Table 3

Factor loading calculated for the q-sorts, q-sorts that are flagged are significantly associated with a factor (source: own calculation with Ken-Q Analysis).

Q sort	Factor 1		Factor 2	Factor 3	
SCJY	0.4519	Flagged	0.3962	0.1837	
KPGR	0.7882	Flagged	0.1635	0.0582	
1X1M	0.8209	Flagged	0.0053	0.0228	
2CLQ	0.8561	Flagged	-0.0021	0.1619	
OY3K	0.6831	Flagged	-0.0263	0.2569	
T5MO	0.6609	Flagged	0.1251	0.319	
NYK2	0.6909	Flagged	-0.1005	0.0478	
8JAI	0.1178		0.6966	Flagged	0.148
AC5H	0.6646	Flagged	0.2478		-0.0071
U6P1	0.127		0.6433	Flagged	0.2441
PYAB	0.45		-0.2703		0.6328
5ZRB	0.1909		0.2916		0.059
7BRE	-0.0156		0.1447		0.6587
E0YL	0.5599	Flagged	0.2792		0.1511
XMDK	0.1512		0.3288		0.805
1EGV	-0.0142		0.6484	Flagged	0.2495
UR3R	0.2954		0.3439		0.3374
YHGW	-0.172		0.7911	Flagged	0.0175
AABH	0.5238		0.4755		0.2925
A7HP	0.5656	Flagged	0.4738		-0.2373
902P	0.0626		0.2953		0.7818
8NYU	0.4058		0.2999		0.4703

the main driver for their farm management decisions (no. 29). They further believe that the market allows farmers to extensify their operations (no. 26), and that food supply chain actors should remunerate public goods (no. 8).

Besides this, they may also be open to participation in AES, they disagree with the statement ‘AES and eco-schemes are for hobby farmers and for farmers on poor quality soils’ (no. 19). Carbon markets may not be suitable to motivate these farmers, they are unlikely to implement the necessary more complex measures (peatland rewetting, agroforestry, afforestation) (no. 6) and oppose result-based payments (no. 16, no. 17).

3.2.2. The traditional food providers

The *traditional food providers* do not share this pro-environmental attitude. Ten statements are distinguishing for them, eleven when those at a lower level of significance are considered. They agree with the statement ‘The Dutch soils are in good condition’ (no. 34). They also state that other measures that determine soil quality (e.g., water holding capacities, soil structure) are more important to them than the soil organic carbon content (no. 5). They further agree that carbon farming activities would limit their ability to run their enterprise in the way that they like (no. 31). This belief can be connected to their perception of being less innovative (no. 27). Carbon markets seem to be especially disliked by these farmers, they perceive them as unattractive and risky (no. 23, no. 20), and they oppose result-based payments (no. 16), and the more complex measures (peatland rewetting, agroforestry and afforestation) (no. 6). They also perceive payments from the food supply chain neutrally (no. 8), and their slight agreement that AES and eco-schemes are for hobby farmers (no. 19) indicates that none of the financial incentives are considered attractive.

3.2.3. The carbon farming pragmatics

The last group represents *carbon farming pragmatics* with nine distinguishing statements, eleven when those significant at a lower level are considered. The group was named *carbon farming pragmatics* as they responded to statements that are relevant for carbon markets (no. 6, no. 10, no. 12, no. 16), even though statement 20, on the viability of carbon markets, is perceived neutrally. The overall findings indicate an interest in carbon markets as an incentive mechanism. They could be an interesting group for promoting carbon markets, as they might implement more complex measures (no. 6) and may be willing to accept a result-based payment (no. 16). To promote their engagement, long-term

Table 4

Q-sort values for identified factors (E: *Pro-environmental Entrepreneurs*, T: *Traditional Food Providers*, C: *Carbon Farming Pragmatics*). Distinguishing statements (Dist.) and consensus statements (Cons.) are marked with x ($p < 0.01$) or (x) ($p < 0.05$) (source: own calculation with K-Q-analysis).

Nr.	Label	Factor 1 (E)	Dist. Factor 1	Factor 2 (T)	Dist. Factor 2	Factor 2 (C)	Dist. Factor 3	Cons.
1	long-term increase	2		0		1		(x)
2	good farm management	3		3		3		x
3	multiple public goods	1		1		2		x
4	resilience to climate change	5	x	0		2		
5	soil structure	-1		5	x	-2		
6	hard measures	-3	x	-5	x	0	x	
7	training & education	-1		0		-5	x	
8	solutions food supply chain	3	x	-1		0		
9	termination option	0		1		2		(x)
10	inflation	0		2		4	x	
11	choose measures	1	(x)	2		2		(x)
12	short tenure	0		0		5	x	
13	long-term contracts	-1		-2		0		(x)
14	farmers' groups	0		1		1		(x)
15	soil sampling costs	-2		-2		-2		x
16	result-based	-4	(x)	-2	(x)	1	x	
17	action-based payments	1	(x)	-1		-1		
18	CAP good incentives	-3		-2		-4		x
19	hobby farmers	-4	x	1	x	-2	x	
20	CM viable	-2		-3	x	0		
21	payment combination	-1		-1		0		x
22	existing initiatives	-1		2	x	-1		
23	CM risky	-2		2	x	0		
24	hybrid payments	0		0		-1	(x)	
25	legislation	1	x	-4		-3		
26	high competition	-3	x	-1	x	3	x	
27	entrepreneurial	2		-3	x	1		
28	greenwashing	0		0		-1	(x)	(x)
29	productivity	1	x	-3		-1		
30	future generations	2	x	-1		-2		
31	freedom to farm	-2		1	x	-3		
32	short-term income	3	x	-4		-4		
33	nature protectionists	2	(x)	4		4		(x)
34	soil conditions are good	-5	x	4	x	-3	x	
35	balance	4		3		3		(x)
36	focus farming	4		3		1	x	

inflation-adjusted payments could be an option (no. 4) or support to encourage longer rental contracts for farmland (no. 5). These aspects could be of special importance to this group as carbon credit trade requires relatively long contracts. However, the business model will need to be sufficiently attractive, as these farmers agree that competition is high, making it difficult to extensify farming practices (no. 26). This helps to explain their perception that training alone is not sufficient to motivate farmers to improve soil health (no. 7). That *carbon farming pragmatics* are more willing to act than *traditional food providers* can be explained by the disagreement of the former with statement 34 'soil conditions are good'.

3.2.4. Consensus statements

Besides these distinguishing statements, some consensus statements are identified. A consensus statement displays similar scores across all groups. These statements show that even though farmers agree that soil health practices are part of good farm management (no. 2), implementing them might come at a cost. Farmers across all groups agree that the public should remunerate the public goods (no. 3), and that the public payments currently on offer are not attractive (no. 18 'The payments offered over the CAP (AES and eco-schemes) are high enough to set financial incentives'). In addition, the statement that combinations of CAP and private payments might be attractive (no. 21) is perceived neutrally.

4. Discussion

The analysis yielded three different viewpoints: (i) *the pro-environmental entrepreneurs*, (ii) *the traditional food providers*, and (iii) *the carbon farming pragmatics*. This section discusses the main

characteristics of these three farmer groups and their evaluations of the different incentives, and provides insights into how to promote soil health measures and carbon farming.

4.1. Incentivising the pro-environmental entrepreneurs

The *pro-environmental entrepreneurs* show a stronger interest in solutions with food value chain partners. Currently, only one experiment looks into value chain contracts that aim at improved soil health (Weituschat et al., 2023). Weituschat et al.'s (2023) article determines farmers' willingness to participate in production contracts under Barilla's sustainable farming initiative, and it strongly focuses on the required measures. They find that farmers who particularly value flexibility tend to show greater interest in such contracts. A review article by Bredemeier et al. (2022) compares experiments on innovative incentives (or contract solutions), and emphasises the potential of value chain payments as these follow a stronger bottom-up approach, and allow more flexibility because contracts are often tailored to the contract parties and not generic like contracts for CAP payments. Bradfield et al. (2023) asked farmers to compare different incentives and find that some expressed interest in value chain payments. However, the authors also note that such contractual arrangements are not yet sufficiently well-known to enable a thorough evaluation.

However, the *pro-environmental entrepreneurs* could also be interested in AES. They disagree that AES is only for hobby farmers and those on low-quality soils (no. 19). It might therefore be that an improved AES is accepted by farmers this group. The finding that farmers display a certain interest in AES compared to carbon markets would also be in line with literature from the US (Canales et al., 2024; Gramig and Widmar, 2018). These authors find that farmers are more interested in AES than

carbon markets because AES more commonly offer action-based payments. Result-based payments are disliked by factor 1 and 2 in the sample. However, the statement leading to this result also suggested that first movers with already high carbon contents in their soils will be excluded (no. 16), and this may therefore require further evaluation.

4.2. Incentivising the carbon farming pragmatics

Some farmers were identified as potentially interested in carbon credit trading. The group referred to as *carbon farming pragmatics* appeared more open to the result based payments required for such schemes and showed a certain willingness to consider stricter measures, such as peatland rewetting or afforestation. The finding that only a few farmers are interested is consistent with results from Germany, where Block et al. (2024) describe limited willingness among farmers to participate in humus programmes, which are similar in structure to carbon credit trading schemes. In contrast, one study by Aslam et al. (2017) suggests that carbon markets may offer sufficient financial incentives to meet farmers' compensation expectations for implementing climate-friendly practices. Nevertheless, Aslam et al. (2017) also note that their use of action-based payments limits comparability, as a defining feature of carbon credit trading is the higher degree of uncertainty regarding outcomes. Other results from experiments considering the EU's QU.A.LITY criteria are still scarce, and for this research it must be noted that the sample is not representative.

Furthermore, it should be critically evaluated if carbon credit trade for soil health measures is likely to become a reality. While the quantification process for EU-certified credits is still undergoing development, certain measures with significant potential for carbon storage and positive co-benefits for biodiversity are already being identified for prioritization. Notably, carbon storage in peat soils, afforestation, and agroforestry are emerging as promising alternatives, both in terms of their scalability and environmental impact (COWI et al., 2021; McDonald et al., 2021; McDonald et al., 2023). Soil health measures are currently subject to critical evaluation, especially because carbon sequestration is easily reversible on farmland (Paul et al., 2023). Studies commonly report a dislike towards more restrictive measures, for instance, by Weituschat et al. (2023) for different practices on arable land, by Norris et al. (2021) for peatland rewetting in the Netherlands and by Dumbrell et al. (2016) for the planting of trees. Farmers in factor 3, however, did not oppose these measures as strongly as factor 1 and factor 2 farmers.

4.3. Incentivising traditional food providers

Farmers that sorted into the second factor, *traditional food providers*, seem less likely to improve their soil health with the help of any of the three suggested incentives. Other soil quality aspects that are closely linked to the production potential are more important for this group than carbon sequestration. However, many improvements, for instance, in soil structure and in the availability of nutrients and water, go hand in hand with higher carbon content (Lal, 2016). This should be emphasised when designing communication strategies targeted at *traditional food providers*.

In addition, research from the Netherlands shows that the inclusion of more soil health-promoting practices (e.g., more cattle manure, more catch crops, and higher grain shares) can increase the income from arable farming in the long run (Kik et al., 2024). Some farmers seem to share this belief already as potential improvements in long-term profitability are described as decisive in various articles on farmers' acceptance of soil health AES or carbon credit contracts (Buck and Palumbo-Compton, 2022; Canales et al., 2024; Tiusanen et al., 2022). In theory, profit-oriented *traditional food providers* should be interested in strategies that increase their income in the long run. That some groups of farmers are difficult to motivate is confirmed by other authors. Their viewpoints are shared by *Commodity Conservationists* and *Jeffersonian*

farmers in Davies and Hodge (2007), and Braito et al.'s (2020) *traditional food providers* and *profit maximisers*. Considering all factors identified in this research, the results that not all farmers respond equally to the available financial incentives can be confirmed (Braito et al., 2020).

4.4. Perception of other incentives

Besides these differences, the experiment also allowed for the identification of statements that the farmers agreed upon. One such common perception is the negative evaluation of the current financial incentives offered via the eco-schemes or AES. Statement No. 2, 'Soil health practices are part of good farm management', is also rather agreed upon. For the *traditional food providers*, the question arises of how to support action. One option to promote pro-environmental action could be through better education for farmers on the effects of climate change on Dutch agriculture. Hail, floods, and storms have already become more common and challenging for Dutch agriculture (The Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality, 2023). Only the *pro-environmental entrepreneurs* believe that their farm will become more resilient to climate change when soil health practices are implemented. The importance of education in fostering more sustainable farming practices is widely recognised. It is highlighted in studies on farmers' willingness to engage in public agri-environmental schemes (Schaub et al., 2023), discussed in the context of value chain contract participation (Weituschat et al., 2023), and emphasised in a Q methodology study exploring the role of extension services in promoting carbon farming (Opdenbosch et al., 2025).

Besides statements that might identify farmers interested in the three central incentive types (public payments, carbon credit trade, and contracts with food value chain partners), some statements referred to additional incentives that could be offered as part of some contracts. One statement that displays a significant impact on the third factor is no. 10, 'inflation.' How to make long-term contracts more attractive deserves more attention, and inflation-adjusted payments could be a solution for contracts including action-based payments. For nature protection, it is commonly described as problematic that farmers are unwilling to opt for contracts with long durations (>10 years) (Harmanny and Schulp, 2023; Mamine et al., 2020; Schaub et al., 2023).

Furthermore, the experiment included a termination option for a successor (no. 9). This was included because Rochecouste et al. (2017) describe that farmers dislike long-term nature conservation and carbon farming contracts because they do not like to limit their flexibility and that of their successors. The statement 'I would find carbon farming contracts more attractive if my successors would be able to leave the contract,' is rather neutrally perceived across all groups. However, the idea should still warrant attention in future experiments.

4.5. Research perspective

From a research perspective, there is also a need for further exploration of all incentives, as one size fits all contract solution do not seem to exist. In the context of value chain contract it could be researched, for instance, what farmers expect from food value chain partners and how to ensure fairness. The article by Weituschat et al. (2023) already investigates value chain contracts for soil health, and it does not cover these aspects. Furthermore, it might be of interest to investigate consumer preferences and whether they respond to soil health claims, as claims for climate neutrality can become more restricted, as the EU aims to regulate the usage of sustainability labels to avoid greenwashing (Mengual et al., 2024).

Researchers and other stakeholders interested in farmers' willingness to engage in carbon credit trade could further explore the carbon credit trade initiatives already set up by groups of farmers. In the Netherlands, such a group is ZLTO, a farmers' organisation that started an early trial with carbon credit trade (ZLTO, 2024). A reason why farmer groups deserve attention is that monitoring costs for carbon

farming are expected to be substantial, and a collective implementation might help to share costs for monitoring and administration (Buck and Palumbo-Compton, 2022; Tiusanen et al., 2022). That farmers may be required to cover soil sampling costs (no. 15) was perceived negatively by all factors, highlighting the need for cost reductions.

There is also potential for researchers to further explore Dutch AES, an important funding source for nature protection and soil health improving measures in the CAP, as the current incentives in AES were negatively perceived by all groups (no. 18). However, both the *pro-environmental entrepreneurs* and the *carbon farming pragmatics* might be interested in improved eco-schemes and AES. This is indicated by their disagreement that these payments are only for hobby farmers (no. 19). Improvements in the CAP payments that lead to higher uptake rates are also of special interest to the Netherlands, where participation rates are among the lowest across Europe (Zimmermann and Britz, 2016). As already said, inflation adjusted payments and the option for successors to discontinue could be an interesting option to motivate farmers, especially when longer contracts should be promoted.

4.6. Strengths and weaknesses of the Q methodology experiment

Finally, a note of caution is necessary. The sample used in this study is not representative of the broader farming population in the Netherlands. As is common in Q Methodology research, the goal was not statistical representativeness but rather to include a diverse range of farmer perspectives, with a portion of the data collected face-to-face. It is possible that farmers with a stronger interest in the topic were more likely to participate, which may have influenced the finding that many respondents expressed interest in value chain payments. A well-known limitation of Q Methodology is that its results are not easily generalisable (Churrucá et al., 2021; Watts and Stenner, 2005). Additionally, the method is often described as time intensive, which makes it difficult to include large samples (Watts and Stenner, 2005). Readers should also be aware that both the selection of statements and the interpretation of the resulting viewpoints can be influenced by the researchers' own perspectives.

Despite these limitations, this study demonstrates the potential of Q Methodology to inform researchers and policymakers about the needs and expectations of specific groups (Barry and Proops, 1999; Zabala et al., 2018). Furthermore, the method facilitates early engagement with stakeholders and helps identify the most promising incentives. This can support the alignment of innovation processes with stakeholder values and contribute to more responsible research and innovation (UKRI, 2023). Moreover, Q Methodology allows for the inclusion of a broad range of statements that reflect various aspects influencing farmers' perceptions of different incentives. In contrast, other methods such as discrete choice experiments are limited in the number of attributes they can include (Marshall et al., 2010), which may restrict the depth of insight into complex decision-making processes.

5. Conclusion

This study identified three distinct farmer perspectives: *pro environmental entrepreneurs*, *traditional food providers*, and *carbon farming pragmatics*. Each group holds different attitudes towards incentives for improving soil health. While *pro environmental entrepreneurs* and *carbon farming pragmatics* may be more open to new incentives such as value chain contracts or carbon farming contracts, *traditional food providers* appear more difficult to engage through these contracts. However, since soil health, carbon storage, and agricultural productivity are closely connected, emphasising these links could help motivate farmers with more conservative views. Although some farmers responded positively to value chain contracts and carbon credit trading, several aspects of these incentives require further consideration before they are widely promoted. For value chain contracts, fairness in negotiating agreements with actors who may have greater market influence is important. It is

also necessary to consider public expectations regarding products that claim to be more sustainable. In the case of carbon credit trade, questions remain about whether soil health measures can deliver the intended long term carbon storage. In addition, the article shows that current public payment schemes are largely rejected. Improving these schemes could increase their acceptance and effectiveness. Overall, the findings demonstrate that farmers have diverse views on soil health incentives. A single contract solution will not meet the needs of all farmers. Tailored approaches that reflect different beliefs, production systems, and market conditions are essential for designing effective and inclusive strategies.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Insa Thiermann: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Francesco Stagni:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Liesbeth Dries:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

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Appendix A. Information provided to the participants (translated into English)

What is Carbon farming (koolstoflandbouw)?

Carbon farming aims to sequester carbon in soils or biomass. Carbon can be stored in soils by applying soil health practices, which are sometimes referred to as regenerative agricultural practices. Other carbon farming methods include afforestation, agroforestry, and the rewetting of peatlands.

The following practices can sequester carbon in soils:

- No or reduced tillage.
- Additional cover crops.
- Leaving cover crops and other plant-based organic materials (straw).
- Usage of compost or other organic fertilisers.
- Broader crop rotations.

Is it worth the effort?

Simulations for typical Dutch arable farms show that the inclusion of regenerative practices increases profits in the long term (40-year simulation).

In the simulations, intensive arable farms (with wheat, potatoes, onions, sugar beets, and carrots) on clay soils could increase their profits by €247.68 per hectare and year and by €292.10 per hectare and year on

sandy soils.

Support for Carbon Farming.

Currently, three different funding types can be used to support the implementation of carbon farming methods, these are:

- Public support (Agri-environmental or eco-schemes).
- Carbon credit trade of EU-certified carbon credits.
- Or private nature protection contracts with actors of the food supply chain.

The funding types have different characteristics, advantages, and disadvantages that are important for the experiment...

Funding type I – Public Support.

Agri-environmental schemes (ANLb – Agrarisch Natuur en Landschapsbeheer) or eco-schemes are examples of public support schemes.

Contract Duration: 1 year for eco-schemes, and 5 years for agri-environmental schemes

Mode of Payment: Payment is often action-based (farmers receive a payment based on the measures they apply).

For example, farmers participating in the ANLb 'Vanggewas na aardappelen' receive €400 per hectare and year if they apply additional catch crops after cultivating potatoes.

Demands: All measures applied under the ANLb or the eco-schemes must exceed standard farm management practices, and the requirements already set in the enhanced conditionality of the CAP.

Important: Budget constraints for agri-environmental and eco-schemes mean that some farmers might not be able to participate in the schemes they are interested in.

Funding type II – Carbon credit trade of EU-certified carbon credits

The legislative framework for the trade of EU-certified Carbon Credits is under development. The following is foreseen:

Mode of Payment: The payment is based on results (the amount of carbon stored per hectare, one credit is one ton of carbon)

Contract Duration: Carbon storage must be guaranteed for a minimum period of ten years after the carbon has been sequestered (the sequestration process may also take ten years)

Demands: Farmers seeking to generate EU-certified carbon credits must fulfil these criteria...

- Quantification: Third parties will certify and monitor the carbon sequestration efforts for the whole duration of the contract. The amount is assumed to be determined by soil samples collected before and after the measures' implementation. The participants have to keep the carbon sequestered; this will be checked (e.g., every three years).
- Additionality: The measures implemented must exceed standard farm management and CAP conditionality requirements.
- Long-term Storage: carbon must be sequestered in the long term (see contract duration).
- Sustainability: the measures cannot affect other sustainability aspects negatively. Therefore, afforestation with monoculture is not allowed.

Important: The sequestered and certified carbon amounts must be held constant; farms are liable for this. Since carbon contents are assumed to fluctuate too strongly in soils, the European Commission prefers peatland rewetting or afforestation as carbon farming measures.

Funding type III: Private nature protection contracts with actors of the food supply chain

Farmers currently stating to be engaged in Carbon Farming are often part of initiative from actors of the food supply chain. The pay farmers for the implementation of practices, as the buyers of carbon offsets seek make sustainability claims (e.g. that they are climate neutral, or promote biodiversity).

Mode of payment: is often hybrid (farmers are partly compensated

for the measures, and receive an additional payment based on the offset)

Contract Duration: often covers periods between 10 or 20 years, starting with implementing the measures.

Important: The European Commission is working on providing a regulation for advertisement claims. It is uncertain whether the actors will be able to make sustainability claims when the demands in their contracts are less strict than the regulation foreseen for carbon credits. The contracts of food value chain partners are criticized for being less strict in terms of the contract durations and monitoring.

Price levels for the trade of carbon offsets: EU-certified carbon credits, and food value chain contracts often foresee a remuneration of € 25 per credit (ton of carbon sequestered). This is assumed to be sufficient to cover the costs of the measures. The prices of the credits may rise if the demand for offsets increases.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Akhtar-Danesh, N., 2018. Qfactor: a command for Q-methodology analysis. *Stata J.* 18 (2), 432–446. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1536867X1801800209>.
- Akhtar-Danesh, N., 2023. Impact of factor rotation on Q-methodology analysis. *PLoS One* 18 (9), e0290728. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0290728>.
- Aslam, U., Termansen, M., Fleskens, L., 2017. Investigating farmers' preferences for alternative PES schemes for carbon sequestration in UK agroecosystems. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 27, 103–112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2017.08.004>.
- Barbato, C.T., Strong, A.L., 2023. Farmer perspectives on carbon markets incentivizing agricultural soil carbon sequestration. *NPJ Clim. Action* 2 (1), 26. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44168-023-00055-4>.
- Barghusen, R., Sattler, C., Deijl, L., Weebers, C., Matzdorf, B., 2021. Motivations of farmers to participate in collective agri-environmental schemes: the case of Dutch agricultural collectives. *Ecosyst. People* 17 (1), 539–555. <https://doi.org/10.1080/26395916.2021.1979098>.
- Barilla, 2022. Barilla Sustainable Agriculture Code. https://www.barillagroup.com/media/file_public/3c/41/3c419716-2fe4-4205-bb13-a25ce56568ff/sac_sustainable_agriculture_code_joint_eng.pdf.
- Barry, J., Proops, J., 1999. Seeking sustainability discourses with Q methodology. *Ecol. Econ.* 28 (3), 337–345. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0921-8009\(98\)00053-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0921-8009(98)00053-6).
- Bartkowski, B., Massenber, J.R., Lienhoop, N., 2022. Investigating preferences for soil-based ecosystem services. *Q Open* 2 (2), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1093/qopen/qaoc035>.
- Block, J.B., Danne, M., Mußhoff, O., 2024. Farmers' willingness to participate in a carbon sequestration program – a discrete choice experiment. *Environ. Manag.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-024-01963-9>.
- Bougherara, D., Gosset, L., Préget, R., Thoyer, S., 2023. Innovativeness. In: *Innovation Adoption and Priming: Nudging Farmers in a Large-scale Randomized Experiment in France Authors (Alphabetical Order)*, pp. 1–27.
- Bradfield, T., Hennessy, T., D'Alberto, R., Haltia, E., 2023. The use of innovative contracts to provide agri-environmental public goods: comparing attitudes between Ireland and other European countries. *Bio-Based Appl. Econ.* 13 (1), 103–120. <https://doi.org/10.36253/bae-14444>.
- Braito, M., Leonhardt, H., Penker, M., Schuppenlehner-Kloyber, E., Thaler, G., Flint, C. G., 2020. The plurality of farmers' views on soil management calls for a policy mix. *Land Use Policy* 99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2020.104876>.
- Bredemeier, B., Herrmann, S., Sattler, C., Prager, K., van Bussel, L.G.J., Rex, J., 2022. Insights into innovative contract design to improve the integration of biodiversity and ecosystem services in agricultural management. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 55, 101430. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2022.101430>.
- Brown, S.R., 2003. Empowerment as subjective operant. In: *Worldbank (Ed.), Measuring Empowerment: Cross-disciplinary Perspectives*. Worldbank.
- Buck, H.J., Palumbo-Compton, A., 2022. Soil carbon sequestration as a climate strategy: what do farmers think? *Biogeochemistry* 161 (1), 59–70. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10533-022-00948-2>.
- Canales, E., Bergtold, J.S., Williams, J.R., 2024. Conservation intensification under risk: an assessment of adoption, additionality, and farmer preferences. *Am. J. Agric. Econ.* 106 (1), 45–75. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ajae.12414>.
- Churrucá, K., Ludlow, K., Wu, W., Gibbons, K., Nguyen, H.M., Ellis, L.A., Braithwaite, J., 2021. A scoping review of Q-methodology in healthcare research. *BMC Med. Res. Methodol.* 21 (1), 125. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-021-01309-7>.
- COWI, Ecologic Institute, IEEP, 2021. Technical Guidance Handbook Setting up and Implementing Result-based Carbon Farming Mechanisms in the EU - Report to the European Commission, DG Climate Action, under Contract No. CLIMA/C.3/ETU/2018/007. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/10acfd66-a740-11eb-9585-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>.
- Davies, B.B., Hodge, I.D., 2007. Exploring environmental perspectives in lowland agriculture: a Q methodology study in East Anglia, UK. *Ecol. Econ.* 61 (2–3), 323–333. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2006.03.002>.

- Dessart, F.J., Barreiro-Hurlé, J., Van Bavel, R., 2019. Behavioural factors affecting the adoption of sustainable farming practices: a policy-oriented review. *Eur. Rev. Agric. Econ.* 46 (3), 417–471. <https://doi.org/10.1093/erae/jbz019>.
- Dumbrell, N.P., Kragt, M.E., Gibson, F.L., 2016. What carbon farming activities are farmers likely to adopt? A best-worst scaling survey. *Land Use Policy* 54, 29–37. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2016.02.002>.
- European Commission, 2023a. Approved 28 CAP Strategic Plans (2023-2027) - Summary Overview for 27 Member States Facts and Figures. <https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-06/approved-28-cap-strategic-plans-2023-27.pdf>.
- European Commission, 2023b. Questions and Answers on a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience. https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/qanda_23_3637.
- European Commission, 2024. Regulation (EU) 2024/3012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 November 2024 Establishing a Union Certification Framework for Permanent Carbon Removals, Carbon Farming and Carbon Storage in Products. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L_202403012.
- European Parliament, 2023. EU to Ban Greenwashing and Improve Consumer Information on Product Durability. <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/press-room/20230918IPR05412/eu-to-ban-greenwashing-and-improve-consumer-information-on-product-durability>.
- Global Compact, 2015. The Barilla Sustainable Farming Project. <http://www.webgallery.globalcompactnetwork.org/web-gallery/12-the-barilla-sustainable-farming-project.html>.
- Gramig, B.M., Widmar, N.J.O., 2018. Farmer preferences for agricultural soil carbon sequestration schemes. *Appl. Econ. Perspect. Policy* 40 (3), 502–521. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aep/pxp041>.
- Guyomard, H., Détang-Dessendre, C., Dupraz, P., Delaby, L., Huyghe, C., Peyraud, J.L., Reboud, X., Sirami, C., 2023. How the green architecture of the 2023–2027 common agricultural policy could have been greener. *Ambio* 52 (8), 1327–1338. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-023-01861-0>.
- Harmanny, K., Schulp, N., 2023. Contracts for the delivery of agri-environmental climate public goods: an overview of the Netherlands. In: Presentation - Joint Meeting EFFECT, CONTRACTS 2.0 & CONSOLE.
- Herzon, I., Birge, T., Allen, B., Povellato, A., Vanni, F., Hart, K., Radley, G., Tucker, G., Keenleyside, C., Oppermann, R., Underwood, E., Poux, X., Beaufoy, G., Pražan, J., 2018. Time to look for evidence: results-based approach to biodiversity conservation on farmland in Europe. *Land Use Policy* 71, 347–354. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2017.12.011>.
- Iofrida, N., De Luca, A.I., Gulisano, G., Strano, A., 2018. An application of Q-methodology to Mediterranean olive production – stakeholders' understanding of sustainability issues. *Agr. Syst.* 162, 46–55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agys.2018.01.020>.
- Jongeneel, R., Gonzalez-Martinez, A., 2023. Implementing the eco-scheme in the Netherlands: a results-based points system approach. *EuroChoices* 22 (1), 20–27. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1746-692X.12388>.
- Kik, M.C., Claassen, G.D.H., Ros, G.H., Meuwissen, M.P.M., Smit, A.B., Saatkamp, H.W., 2024. FARManalytics – a bio-economic model to optimize the economic value of sustainable soil management on arable farms. *Eur. J. Agron.* 157. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2024.127192>.
- Laijshram, J.L., Saxena, K.G., Maikhuri, R.K., Rao, K.S., 2012. Soil quality and soil health: a review. *Int. J. Ecol. Environ. Sci.* 38 (1), 19–37. <http://www.researchgate.net/publication/232237296>.
- Lal, R., 2016. Soil health and carbon management. *Food Energy Secur.* 5 (4), 212–222. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fes3.96>.
- Lapierre, M., Le Velly, G., Bougherara, D., Préget, R., Sauquet, A., 2023. Designing agri-environmental schemes to cope with uncertainty. *Ecol. Econ.* 203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2022.107610>.
- Loomis, J., Gascoigne, W., 2018. Understanding agricultural producers' willingness to undertake self-monitoring of environmental outcomes: results of a choice experiment with Colorado agricultural producers. *J. Nat. Resour. Policy Res.* 8 (1–2), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.5325/naturesopolirese.8.1-2.0001>.
- Mamine, F., Fares, M., Minviel, J.J., 2020. Contract design for adoption of agri-environmental practices: a meta-analysis of discrete choice experiments. *Ecol. Econ.* 176, 1–12.
- Marshall, D., Bridges, J.F.P., Hauber, B., Cameron, R., Donnelly, L., Fyfe, K., Johnson, F. R., 2010. Conjoint analysis applications in health – how are studies being designed and reported? *Patient-Center. Outcom. Res.* 3 (4), 249–256. <https://doi.org/10.2165/11539650-000000000-00000>.
- McCaig, M., Reznia, D., Dara, R., 2023. Framing the response to IoT in agriculture: a discourse analysis. *Agric. Syst.* 204, 103557. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.AGSY.2022.103557>.
- McDonald, H., Frelüh-Larsen, A., Lóránt, A., Duin, L., Andersen, S.P., Costa, G., Bradley, H., 2021. Carbon Farming Making Agriculture Fit for 2030.
- McDonald, H., Siemons, A., Bodle, R., Hobeika, M., Scheid, A., Schneider, L., McDonald, H., 2023. QU.A.L.I.T.Y Soil Carbon Removals? Assessing the EU Framework for Carbon Removal Certification From a Climate-friendly Soil Management Perspective Ecologic Institute. QU.A.L.I.T.Y Soil Carbon Removals? Assessing the EU framework for Carbon Removal Certification From a Climate-friendly Soil Management Perspective Contact Suggested Citation. www.ecologic.eu.
- Mengual, S., Boschiero, E., Leite, J., Casonato, C., Mancini, L., Sinkko, T., Wollgast, J., Listori, G., Sala, S., 2024. Sustainability Labelling in the EU Food Sector: Current Status and Coverage of Sustainability Aspects. <https://doi.org/10.2760/498001>.
- Norris, J., Matzdorf, B., Barghusen, R., Schulze, C., van Gorcum, B., 2021. Viewpoints on cooperative peatland management: expectations and motives of dutch farmers. *Land* 10 (12). <https://doi.org/10.3390/land10121326>.
- Opendbosch, H., Hansson, H., Källström, H.N., Manevska-Tasevska, G., 2025. Upscaling carbon farming practices: perceived advisor leverage in farmer decision-making using Q-methodology. *J. Agric. Educ. Ext.* 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1389224X.2025.2533173>.
- Paul, C., Bartkowski, B., Dönmez, C., Don, A., Mayer, S., Steffens, M., Weigl, S., Wiesmeier, M., Wolf, A., Helming, K., 2023. Carbon farming: are soil carbon certificates a suitable tool for climate change mitigation? *J. Environ. Manage.* 330. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.117142>.
- Q Method Software, 2024. Q Method Software - An Easy-to-Use Tool to Create & Conduct Your Q Methodology Research Online. <https://qmethodsoftware.com>.
- Rabobank, 2022. Rabo Carbon Bank Sells First Carbon Credits to Dutch Companies. <https://www.rabobank.com/about-us/carbon-bank/011264819/rabo-carbon-bank-sells-first-carbon-credits-to-dutch-companies>.
- Recare-Hub, 2018. Olden Eibergen, The Netherlands. <https://www.recare-hub.eu/case-studies/olden-eibergen-the-netherlands#:~:text=The%20loss%20of%20soil%20or%20ganic%20matter%20in%20the%20area%20is,their%20farms%20above%20the%20threshold>.
- Rocheouste, J.F., Dargusch, P., King, C., 2017. Farmer perceptions of the opportunities and constraints to producing carbon offsets from Australian dryland grain cropping farms. *Aust. J. Environ. Manag.* 24 (4), 441–452. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14486563.2017.1379037>.
- Runge, T., Langlais, A., Cardwell, M., 2022. Legal Aspects of Contract Solutions to Foster the Provision of Agri Environment Climate Goods. https://literatur.thuenen.de/diglib_extern/dn065563.pdf.
- Sandling, J., 2024. Q Methodology a Beginner's Guide, p. 2024. <https://jonathansandling.com/q-methodology-complete-beginners-guide/>.
- Schaub, S., Ghazoul, J., Huber, R., Zhang, W., Sander, A., Rees, C., Banerjee, S., Finger, R., 2023. The role of behavioural factors and opportunity costs in farmers' participation in voluntary agri-environmental schemes: a systematic review. *J. Agric. Econ.* <https://doi.org/10.1111/1477-9552.12538>.
- Schulze, C., Zagórska, K., Häfner, K., Markiewicz, O., Czajkowski, M., Matzdorf, B., 2023. Using farmers' ex ante preferences to design agri-environmental contracts: a systematic review. *J. Agric. Econ.* <https://doi.org/10.1111/1477-9552.12570>.
- Silvius, H., Voskuilen, M., Kuiper, P.P., van Essen, E., 2016. Grondsoort en grondprij. <https://edepot.wur.nl/394962#:~:text=De%20belangrijkste%20grondsoorten%20in%20Nederland,hoofdzaak%20in%20Zuid%20Limburg>.
- Stephenson, W., 1953. *The Study of Behavior: Q-Technique and Its Methodology*, 1st ed. Chicago University Press.
- Terwan, P., 2016. The Cooperative Approach Under the New Dutch Agri-environment-climate Scheme Background, Procedures and Legal and Institutional Implications. https://www.rbpnetwork.eu/media/lr_95078_dutch_agri_enviromentdef.pdf.
- The Ministry of Agriculture Nature and Food Quality, 2023. International Exchange on Climate Adaptation in Agriculture.
- Tiusanen, K., Lampinen, A., Hukkoniemi, V., Harjama, N., Rimhanen, K., Ilvesniemi, H., Juuso Joona, L., Farm Kaj Granholm, T., Naukkarinen, V., Marianne Tikkanen, B., 2022. LIFE Carbon Farming Scheme Final Report: Guidance for Future Carbon Farming Schemes Best Practices for Expanding Carbon Sequestration Activities. <https://content.stl.fi/sites/default/files/2022-06/LIFE%20Carbon%20Farming%20Scheme%20final%20report%2001062022.pdf>.
- UKRI, 2023. Framework for Responsible Research and Innovation. <https://www.ukri.org/who-we-are/epsrc/our-policies-and-standards/framework-for-responsible-innovation/>.
- van der Meulen, H., 2024. Areaal en aantal bedrijven. <https://agratie.nl/SectorResultaat.aspx?subpubID=2232§orID=2233#>.
- Villanueva, A.J., Glenk, K., Rodríguez-Entrena, M., 2017. Protest responses and willingness to accept: ecosystem services providers' preferences towards incentive-based schemes. *J. Agric. Econ.* 68 (3), 801–821. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1477-9552.12211>.
- Voskuilen, M., 2024. Bedrijfsstructuur: lichte daling aantal bedrijven in 2022. <https://agratie.nl/ThemaResultaat.aspx?subpubID=2232&themaID=2286&indicatorID=3049>.
- Watts, S., Stenner, P., 2005. Doing Q methodology: theory, method and interpretation. *Qual. Res. Psychol.* 2 (1), 67–91. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088705qp0220a>.
- Webler, T., Danielson, S., Tuler, S., 2009. Using Q Method to Reveal Social Perspectives in Environmental Research (Online). Social and Environmental Research Institute. <https://www.betterevaluation.org/sites/default/files/Qprimer.pdf>.
- Weitschat, C.S., Pascucci, S., Matera, V.C., Caracciolo, F., 2023. Can contract farming support sustainable intensification in Agri-food value chains? *Ecol. Econ.* 211, 107876. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2023.107876>.
- Wetlands International, 2023. A Definition of Paludiculture in the CAP. <https://europe.wetlands.org/publications/what-does-paludiculture-mean-a-definition/>.
- Zabala, A., 2014. Qmethod: a package to explore human perspectives using Q methodology. *R J.* 6 (2), 163–173.
- Zabala, A., Sandbrook, C., Mukherjee, N., 2018. When and how to use Q methodology to understand perspectives in conservation research. *Conserv. Biol.* 32 (5), 1185–1194. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.13123>.
- Zimmermann, A., Britz, W., 2016. European farms' participation in agri-environmental measures. *Land Use Policy* 50, 214–228. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2015.09.019>.
- ZLTO, 2024. Carbon Farming: koolstofboeren in Zeeland. <https://www.zlto.nl/projecten/carbon-farming>.